

Date Accessed (of search)	Search (Search term used)	Origin of website (e.g. Knowledge of Researcher, found in X documentation ...)	(Primary) Website	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social Care; Education)	High level finding (data we are interested in)	National; Regional or Cantonal	Experts Identified	Experts Note	New Website Identified	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social Care)	Note	New Website Identified - Used as search?
12.02.2018	Univerza v Ljubljani	Partner organisation	https://www.unl.si/en/	Research institutes	Research institutes	-	National	-	-	http://www.ipp.si/home	Research institutes	Research institutes	-	Y
12.02.2018	http://www.ipp.si/home	From https://www.unl.si/eng/	http://www.ipp.si/home	Research institutes	Research institutes	-	National	prof. dr. Viktorija Znidaršič Skubic	Area of expertise: civil law, civil medical law, family law, inheritance law T: 01/ 42 03 152 E: viktorija.znidarsic@pf.u-nl.si	-	-	-	-	-
13.02.2018		Letters of intent	http://www.zveza.gns.si/o-zvezi/zakonodaja/	NGO	Disability	-	National	-	-	https://www.uradni-list.si/glasilo-uradni-list-rs/vsebina?urid=201158&stevilka=2714#	Government website (National)?	Government website (National)?	-	Y
13.02.2018	https://www.uradni-list.si/glasilo-uradni-list-rs/vsebina?urid=201158&stevilka=2714#	From Zveza društev gluhih in naglušnih Slovenij	https://www.uradni-list.si/glasilo-uradni-list-rs/vsebina?urid=201158&stevilka=2714#	Government website (National)?	Government website (National)?	2714. Zakon o usmerjanju otrok s posebnimi potrebami (ZUOPP-1), stran 8424 (Law promoting the education of children with special needs)	National	-	-	http://www.rpls.si/	-	-	They define "children with special needs" as children with mental, behavioral or emotional disorders, blind, deaf, with impairment or long-term illness. YC are not included.	Y
13.02.2018	http://www.rpls.si/	From https://www.uradni-list.si/glasilo-uradni-list-rs/vsebina?urid=201158&stevilka=2714#	http://www.rpls.si/	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-	National	-	-	http://www.pisrs.si/Pis_web/	-	-	Register collecting regulations from municipalities.	Y
13.02.2018	http://www.pisrs.si/Pis_web/	From https://www.uradni-list.si/glasilo-uradni-list-rs/vsebina?urid=201158&stevilka=2714#	http://www.pisrs.si/Pis_web/	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Document: List of Slovenian laws and regulations in English	National	-	-	PDF: List of Slovenian laws and regulations in English	Other	Other	Legal informatio system	Y
14.02.2018	PDF: List of Slovenian laws and regulations in English	From http://www.pisrs.si/Pis_web/akonodajaRSanglescina	PDF: List of Slovenian laws and regulations in English	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Public Interest in Youth Sector Act: this Act defines the youth sector and sets out the public interest in the youth sector as well as the method of implementing the public interest in the youth sector.	National	-	-	-	-	-	No information about YCs nor family caregivers nor children rights	-
14.02.2018	Young carers in Slovenia	Google search	http://www.inst-antonatrstenjaka.si/slike/103-1.pdf	Research institutes	Research institutes	Until few years ago, Slovenia had no national policy that would deal with family carers directly. There were some acts, which indirectly concerned family carers and only one that enables family carers as family assistants to get, under specific rules, a financial compensation. An important document for family carers of old people was adopted in Slovenia in April 2006 – the National Social Protection Programme 2006-2010 (ReNPSV06-10 2006). One of its goals is the support to the family and social networks at caring for people in need of help.	National	-	-	-	-	-	Written in 2009	-
15.02.2018	Children's rights in slovenia	Google search	https://www.humanium.org/en/slovenia/	International organisations	International organisations	In Slovenia, the situation of children is good, for the most part, for many years now, the country has adopted important measures and continues its efforts to guarantee and to protect Human Rights, specifically, Rights of the Child. However, serious problems (discrimination, domestic violence, human trafficking...) persist and require attention from Slovenian authorities.	National	-	-	-	-	-	Nothing about caring	-
15.02.2018	Children's rights in slovenia	Google search	http://www.mddsc.gov.si/fileadmin/mddsc.gov.si/pageuploads/dokument__pdf/pom2006_2016_en.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Basic principles: IV. Every child has the right to life, personal and social security, growth and healthy development. [...] Children must furthermore be given the chance for quality free time, play, cultural endeavours and entertainment, which are all integral parts of their upbringing. (p. 6) Social policy: one aim is to achieve better efficiency in supporting and helping children and their families. Free time activities policy: the basic objective is to provide to the highest extent possible the possibilities for quality free time experiences for all groups of children and youth. (p. 24)	National	-	-	-	-	-	Document about several children's rights, including health, social policies and quality of free time. However, it doesn't include anything about caregiving.	-
15.02.2018	Family caregiver Slovenia	Google search	http://www.inst-antonatrstenjaka.si/slike/103-1.pdf	Research institutes	Research institutes	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.02.2018	Universities in Slovenia	Google search	http://studyinslovenia.si/study/universities-and-institutions/	Research institutes	Research institutes	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	Looked at the law faculties of the University of Maribor and the European Faculty of Law, Nova Gorica; found nothing relevant	-
16.02.2018	law research in slovenia	Google search	http://www.nyulawglobal.org/globalex/Slovenia.html	?	?	General information about Slovenian political system	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.02.2018	Informal caregivers Slovenia	Google search	http://www.fs.fv.org/wp-content/uploads/2011/12/ibeber-Valentina-Sue	International organisations	?	The Health Care and Health Insurance Act (1992) offers an opportunity for family members to take care of a close family member. They are eligible for wage compensation (80%) for 7 days, exceptionally for 14 days, but only for people who are living in the same household.	National	-	-	Nagode, Jakob Krejan, Smolej (2010): IZVAJANJE POMOČI NA DOMU. Analiza stanja v letu 2010. Končno poročilo (Home care. Analysis of 2010 data. Final report). Social Protection Institute of RS.	Research institutes	Research institutes	Written by Valentina	Y
16.02.2018	Nagode, Jakob Krejan, Smolej (2010): IZVAJANJE POMOČI NA DOMU. Analiza stanja v letu 2010. Končno poročilo (Home care. Analysis of 2010 data. Final report). Social Protection Institute of RS.	From http://www.ifa-fiv.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/12/ibeber-Valentina-Support-for-Caregivers-in-Slovenia-Interplay-of-Transition-and-Ageing.pdf	Nagode, Jakob Krejan, Smolej (2010): IZVAJANJE POMOČI NA DOMU. Analiza stanja v letu 2010. Končno poročilo (Home care. Analysis of 2010 data. Final report). Social Protection Institute of RS.	Research institutes	Research institutes	-	-	-	-	www.umar.gov.si/fileadmin/user_upload/././DZ_02_14.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Secured document, not possible to translate it in Google	Y

16.02.2018	www.umar.gov.si/fileadmin/user_upload/.../D2_02_14.pdf	From Nagode, Jakob Krejan, Smolej (2010): IZVAJANJE POMOČI NA DOMU. Analiza stanja v letu 2010. Končno poročilo (Home care. Analysis of 2010 data. Final report). Social Protection Institute of RS.	www.umar.gov.si/fileadmin/user_upload/.../D2_02_14.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	In Slovenia there is no valid uniform definition of long-term care, the area is not even systematically regulated (eg by a special law). Long-term care is currently governed by various laws and regulations, namely: - Pension and disability insurance; - Health insurance; - Insurance for parental protection; - Social benefits and social welfare services; - Caring for war veterans; - Within the framework of the Social Protection Act for the mentally and physically disabled An umbrella law regulating the field of long-term care is under preparation. Recently, three proposals for a law on long-term care were prepared - one was created under the auspices of the Ministry of Labor, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, the second under the auspices of the Association of Pensioners' Associations of Slovenia and the third one within the Community of Social Institutes of Slovenia.	National	Davor Dominkuš	Secretary at the Ministry of Labor, Family, Social Affairs and equal opportunities. Co-author Sociologist: From 1987 to 1997 he was director of the Institute for Training of Disabled Youth in Kamnik. After coming to the Ministry of Labor, Family and Social Affairs, he was employed at the Directorate for Social Welfare. davor.dominkus@gov.si	-	-	-	Workbook presenting the use of the international definition of long-term care at the national level.	-
19.02.2018	Children as next of kin slovenia	Google search	https://www.ined.fr/Xtradocs/lawsandfamilies/LawsAndFamilies-SI-Section2.pdf	Research institutes	Research institutes	LawsAndFamilies Database – Aspects of legal family formats for same-sex and different-sex couples	National	Dr. Barbara Rajželj	Author and assistant professor of civil and corporate law, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana; and Institute for culture of diversity Open	-	-	-	Nothing about young carers	-
19.02.2018	Children as next of kin slovenia	Google search	http://ec.europa.eu/justice/publications/docs/summary_right/slovenia_2.pdf	Research institutes	Research institutes	-	National	Suzana Kraljič	Author, she currently works as associate professor at the Faculty of Law, University of Maribor. Her primary interest of research is Family Law and Medical Law. She is also teaching on child rights in Pre-school Education and Primary Education.	-	-	-	Written in 2005 Nothing about young carers, more about custody	-
21.02.2018	Mladi skrbnik	Google search	http://cod.mb.si/o-nas/kontakti-zaposlenih/	Government website (local)	Social care	List of experts working in the social field and for the protection of children and adolescents.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
27.02.2018	Pravic Mladi skrbni	Google search	http://www.vrhuha.si/otroci-mladi/o-otrokovih-pravicah/kaj-so-otrokov-pravice/	Government website (national)	Government website (national)	-	National	Vlasta Nussdorfer	She graduated from the Faculty of Law in Ljubljana and, as a senior state prosecutor, she served as head of the Department for Juvenile, Family and Sexual Crime at the District State Prosecutor's Office in Ljubljana. Since 2013 she is Human Rights Ombudsman.	http://en.zpms.si/home/	NGO	Youth organisations	Ombudsman website of the Republic of Slovenia.	Y
27.02.2018	http://en.zpms.si/home/	From http://www.vrhuha.si/otroci-mladi/o-otrokovih-pravicah/kaj-so-otrokov-pravice/	http://en.zpms.si/home/	NGO	Youth organisations	Slovenian Association of Friends of Youth aims: - to promote and implement the convention on the rights of the child, - to raise the quality of children, youth and family life, - to reduce social exclusion of children, youth and families, - to give opportunities to experience active spare time, - to motivate individuals and organizations to positive statements about children, youth and families, - to promote voluntary work, - to develop and support cooperation with non-governmental associations in Slovenia and abroad, - to help children and young people to create positive self-image - to form positive attitudes and values to life	National	Darja Groznik	ZPMS President darja.groznik@zpms.si	-	-	-	-	-
								Petra Zega	Field of work: children's rights, "children's Parliament" petra.zega@zpms.si					
								Sara Geiger Smole	Field of work: advocacy and information centre on the rights of children and adolescents. sara.geiger.smole@zpm.si					
28.02.2018	Pravic Mladi skrbni	Google search	https://www.rtvso.si/strani/mate-pravice/271	News websites	News websites	-	National	-	-	www.unicef.si	International organisations	Youth organisations	-	Y
										www.vrhuha.si				N
										www.rs-swel.net				Y
										www.djanska.org				Y
										www.unicef.si				Y
28.02.2018	www.unicef.si	From https://www.rtvso.si/strani/mate-pravice/271	www.unicef.si	International organisations	Youth organisations	Among other principles, UNICEF Slovenia states that steps must be taken to reduce drop-outs in secondary schools and increase the inclusion of unemployed youth in training and education programs.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

01.03.2018	www.na-svet.net	From https://www.rtvslo.si/strani/i-mate-pravice/271	www.na-svet.net	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Webpage can't be found	-
01.03.2018	www.tipovej.org	From https://www.rtvslo.si/strani/i-mate-pravice/271	www.tipovej.org	NGO	Youth organisations	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
01.03.2018	www.dijaska.org	From https://www.rtvslo.si/strani/i-mate-pravice/271	www.dijaska.org	NGO	Youth organisations	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Dijaška organizacija Slovenije (DOS) brings together all Slovenian students, represents their interests and advocates their realization.	-
01.03.2018	www.izpisa.pms.si	From https://www.rtvslo.si/strani/i-mate-pravice/271	www.izpisa.pms.si	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Webpage can't be found	-